

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 1.13

A CRITICAL STUDY ON SMALL SCALE SECTOR BEFORE AND AFTER LIBERALIZATION

DR. C. M. JAIN ,

Head, department of accounts and law,
faculty of commerce, St.johns college

Agra

Dr. Neeraj Manchanda,

Assistant Proessor, faculty of commerce,
Agra college, Agra

ABSTRACT

Small Scale Industries play a significant role in terms of their socio-economic worth for India. India is a leading developing nation of the world. India faces numerous socio-economic challenges today. Unemployment and poverty are among the most crucial problems being faced by India. With liberalization, Indian economy has got transformed into a vibrant open economy. Now, multinational companies can easily enter our nation and do business. This kind of interaction with world economy is no doubt required for the overall healthy growth of a nation but it is harsh socio-economic reality that multinational companies cannot match the employment generating potential of small scale Industries. Socio-economic relevance of small scale industry is quite obvious. SSI are playing meaningful role in export sector of the nation. Persistent efforts are required to promote SSI in India as a source of employment generation on a large scale and equitable distribution of income. These small scale industries have substantially grown during last few decades. Participation and involvement of women entrepreneurs will further promote meaningful role of Indian small scale industries in Indian economy.

Key words: Small Scale, socio-economic, Leberalisation, India

INTRODUCTION

The small scale industries plays an important role in job creation and employment. It further gives competition to large monopoly players and lay the foundation of sound economy. The government has been following a policy of reservation of items for exclusive development in the small scale sector. The rapid growth of small scale industries has a great relevance in the national economic policies of India. Owing to the dearth of capital, India cannot easily build up large scale industries. So, the small scale industries can offer the large volume of employment. The farmers may be employed in the small and cottage industries during the idle season with a view to improving their economic conditions. India has accepted the ideals of socialistic pattern of society. In order to attain this goal, it is necessary to prevent the rise of monopolistic units of production. This objective can be achieved by promoting the small scale and cottage industries. The cottage and small scale industries are able to produce goods with artistic design and the cost of production is very low. Besides, these industries provide good opportunities for self employment.

India is a land of agriculture. About 70% of the total population depends on agriculture for their livelihood. This results in endless sub-division and fragmentation of holdings. The cottage and small scale industries should be promoted so that the surplus people can depend

on them. Moreover there is no need of foreign exchange resources for the development of small scale and cottage industries. Hence these industries may be able to solve the balance of payment difficulties and also check the inflationary pressure in India.

Indian economic system is a classical example of mixed economy where both public and private sector work hand in hand. Seeing India's vast population and various socio-economic challenges which she faces, presence of public sector is justified as revenue generated from this sector can help resolving some problems at least. The Indian economy currently stands among the world's fourth largest growing economy in terms of purchasing power parity and holds the distinction of being a key contributor to Asia's balance of payment surplus. India's economic development has brought tremendous success for the country with a better global image. 8 percent growth rate of India's national income for consecutive years is a true indication of its growth story.

The infrastructure related problems as a threat to country's economic development is being solved to some extent through public, private, domestic and foreign investments. The trends in India's foreign exchange reserves demonstrate a comfortable level, consistent with the rate of growth, the share of external sector in the economy and the size of risk-adjusted capital inflow.

Objectives:

1. To analyse the role of SSI in Indian Economy.
2. To study the trend of SSI before and after 1991.

Study is based on Secondary Data

Indian economy is a classical example of a developing economy with vast population and geographical area. Indian economy is the leading developing economy of the world. India is facing typical socio-economic problems which are continuing in various shapes, forms and composition since ages. It will not be unfair to say that current state of affairs in Indian economy are not in tune with true essence and spirit of democratisation. Mostly richer sections of the society are reaping benefits of economic progress. Small Scale Industries have a unique potential to address many such problems. India's GDP is increasing but more important is the satisfactory increase in the per capita income. It can be achieved by generation of employment and boost to entrepreneurship by upliftment of small scale industries. Small scale units can play a meaningful role in democratizing Indian economy thus making it more people friendly and capable of addressing socio-economic problems in an emphatic manner.

Low per capita income- Compared with the developed countries of the west, Indian economy was appallingly poor in the early 1950s, and since then its economic distance with them has steadily increased. On the basis of per capita income, India was among the few poorest countries at the time of independence. This poverty and backwardness India had inherited from the colonial rule.

After Independence the government wanted to give a 'big push' to the standstill economy and for this purpose, it employed the technique of 'democratic planning'.

With the efforts of the government some development has indeed taken place during the five decades of planning, but India still remains one of the most underdeveloped countries in term of per capita income. One can have some idea of the plight of the people of this country from the fact that, India still remains a low income economy.

According to world Development Report 2007, India was one of the 45 low income economies in 2005. Thus per capita GNP was higher in all the middle and higher income economies than in India. Even in the category of low income economies as many as seven countries had higher per capita GNP than that in India. The economic distance between the most developed countries and India has also increased over the years. In 2005 India's Purchasing Power Parity estimate of GNP per capita was as low as \$ 3,460. It was around one-twelfth of the U.S.A.'s PPP estimate of GNP per capita which stood at \$ 41,950 in that year. No doubt national income statistics of various countries are not comparable because of the differences in respect of concept of national income and degree of reliability of data; nevertheless, for broad comparisons they can be gainfully used. Therefore when we discover from these data that India's PPP estimate of GNP per capita is around one- ninth of GNP per capita of developed countries (which stood at \$ 32,524 in 2005), we not only learn about the existing plight of the people in this country, but also know about the stupendous task which this country has ahead of it.

Inequitable distribution of income- The distribution of income and wealth in India is inequitable. This is not at all surprising because private ownership of means of production inevitably leads to concentration of wealth in a few hands. Income inequalities result from the concentration of wealth and capital. The government and the economic planners were aware of the economic inequalities in the early 1950s but they were possibly ignorant of the fact the economic growth in an essentially capitalist economy has a tendency to accentuate disparities in income distribution.

In 1997, according to World Development Report 2000/2001, while the lowest 40 per cent households accounted for 19.7 per cent of the aggregate household expenditure in India, the share of top 20 per cent in it was as large as 46 per cent. In the middle category 40 per cent household at modest level of living accounted for 34.3 per cent of the aggregate household expenditure. The Gini Lorenz Ratio was 0.378 in 1997 as against 0.297 in 1994. Thus during the 1990s inequalities in household consumption expenditure had increased as a result of pro-rich liberalization policies.

High Incidence of poverty - The problem of mass poverty is a natural outcome of income inequalities. The planning commission acknowledges the fact of widespread poverty in the country in the Sixth Five Year Plan 1980-1985. The plan document stated that using norms of calorie consumption, the per cent in rural areas and 40.3 per cent in urban areas. For the country as a whole the percentage of poor was as high as 48.44.

According to the planning commission, the overall percentage of the people below the poverty line had declined to 36.0 per cent in 1993-94 while the incidence of poverty was 37.3 per cent in rural areas and 32.4 per cent in urban areas. Now the latest estimates of incidence of poverty are available for 2004-05. These estimates are based on the data made available from the consumer Expenditure Survey of the 61st Round. According to

these estimates, the poverty ratio was 27.8 per cent at the national level if Uniform Recall Period (URP) was used. In URP, data on consumption expenditure for all items are obtained from 30 days recall period. Incidence of poverty at the national level was 22 per cent in 2004-05 if Mixed Recall Period (MRP) was used. In MRP, data for 5 non-food items, namely, clothing fertilizers, durable goods, education and institutional medical expenses are collected from 365 days recall. Consumption expenditure data for other items are obtained from a 30 days recall period. However, these estimates are not strictly comparable with the earlier estimates due to changes in methodology of collecting data.

The latest comparable estimates from URP are available from 54th round of the NSS for the January 1998 -June 1998 which show that 44.9 per cent population in rural areas and 31.6 per cent population in urban areas was below the poverty line. These estimates show that since the late 1970s there has been a decline in incidence of poverty. Nevertheless, the percentage of population below the poverty line is still quite high.

Predominance of Agriculture- Occupational distribution of population in India is not at all satisfactory and clearly reflects the economic backwardness of the economy. In 1951 about 249 million people, that is, about 70 per cent of the population of the country was dependent on agriculture for its subsistence. Since then very little change has occurred in the situation. Even when we consider the working population we reach the same conclusion. In 1951 around 69.7 per cent of the working population was employed in agriculture. As against this, in 1991 around 66.9 per cent of the working population was absorbed in agriculture operations. NSSO and ministry of labour have, however, pointed out that there has been a significant decline in employment in agriculture during the 1990s in percentages terms. In 2001, 58.9 per cent of main workers were employed in agriculture and allied activities. Thus agriculture still remains the biggest employer in India.

A second indicator of the predominance of agriculture in the Indian economy is the proportion of national income originating in this sector. In 2005 agriculture contributed 19 per cent of the Gross Domestic Product. This is indeed substantially less than the share of agriculture in Gross Domestic Product in 1950-51(when it contributed more than 50 per cent).

Rapid population growth and high dependency ratio- Over the years population in India has been growing at a fast rate. According to the estimates of the 2001 Census, the population of India was 1,025 million as against 439 million in 1961. Thus population in India over these years had increased roughly at the rate of 2.14 per cent per annum and according to the present indications it appears that the rate of population growth may not decline substantially in the immediate future. The country is at present passing through the second stage of demographic transition which is characterized by a falling death rate without a corresponding decline in birth rate. This has resulted in population explosion partly offsetting the small gains of development which this country had made during the planning period. J.J. Spengler has argued that an increase in population raises the ratio of people to land and other sources of raw materials and as a consequence, production trends to decline per unit of variable cost in the concerned industries. The trend is clearly discernible in Indian agriculture. Over the years per head agricultural land has steadily declined in this country on account of rapid

growth of population. Land reclamation which was possible only at modest scale was not enough to offset the increasing pressure of population on agriculture land. The pressure of population on agriculture land in a country can be reduced only if it is possible to transfer some population to other sectors of economic activities. But in India, growth of industries and commerce has been rather sluggish and inter-sectoral transfer to population has not been possible. Consequently, the pressure of population on agriculture land continues to grow swelling the number of disguised unemployed. In India rapid growth of population has also resulted in a high dependency ratio. In 1999-2000 percentage of population of working age (15-64 years) in India was 63.8 as against 66.9 in developed market economies.

Low level of human development- Human development is usually measured in terms of Human Development Index (HDI) constructed by the United Nations Development Programmed (UNDP). The HDI is a composite of three basic indicators of human development - longevity, knowledge and standard of living. Longevity is measured by life expectancy at birth; knowledge (or educational attainment) by a combination of adult literacy (two- thirds weight) and combined primary, secondary tertiary ratios (one- third weight) and combined primary, secondary and tertiary ratios (one- third weight); and standard of living is measured by real GDP per capita (purchasing power parity, PPP in dollars).

Human Development Report 2006 presents HDI value and ranking for some developed and developing countries and their comparison with real GDP per capita ranking.

India with a HDI value of 0.611 ranks a lowly 126 in terms of HDI. China with HDI value of 0.768 and Sri Lanka with HDI value of 0.755 ranked 81 and 93 respectively. On the basis of the HDI ranking calculated for 177 countries, Human Development Report 2006 places 63 countries in the high human development category. In this category besides the developed country, some developing countries like Cyprus, Barbados, Argentina, Uruguay, Cuba and Mexico are included. In the medium human development category, there are 83 countries. The more prominent countries in this category are Brazil, Thailand, Sri Lanka, China, Vietnam, Indonesia, India and Bangladesh. 31 countries comprise the low human development category. Rwanda, Cameroon, Kenya, Zambia, Nigeria, Senegal, Madagascar and Ethiopia figure in the low human development category.

Unemployment- Widespread unemployment is perhaps the most striking symptom of inadequate development in India. Since 1972-73 reliable estimates of unemployment are available from the various Rounds of the NSSO (National Sample Survey Organisation) surveys. These estimates are in terms of three concepts: the usual status, the weekly status and the daily status. Estimates of the usual status indicate only the open unemployment. The more comprehensive measure of unemployment, however, is in terms of the daily status unemployment. Presently the latest estimates of unemployment are available for 2004-05 from the 61st Round of NASSO. According to these estimates, in 2004-05 the current daily status unemployment rate for rural and urban male workers was 8.0 and 7.5 per cent respectively. Considering the fact that employment elasticities in major sector have been falling drastically since 1983, these rates seem to be underestimates of unemployment.

Moreover, this fact cannot be ignored that in recent years absolute number of the unemployed has risen. According to the planning commission current daily status unemployed at the end of 2001-02 was 3.49 crore. During the 1990s unemployed situation deteriorated. The results of the latest 61st round of the National Sample Survey (NSS) show that unemployment had indeed gone up by 4-5 per cent, as per the usual status. Using the daily status figures which are more acceptable measure of employment, the unemployment level had gone up by 9-10 per cent between 1999-2000 and 2004-05.

The nature of unemployment in India is different from that in developed countries. Most of the unemployment to be found in the developed countries of the west is cyclical. In contrast unemployment in India is chronic and results from the structural defects in the economy. People in a large number in the countryside do not have adequate work throughout the year and many of them suffer from disguised unemployment for long periods. According to Ragnar Nurkse, if some of these people are removed from agriculture and absorbed in another productive activity, farm output may not fall, while the national income will increase due to their productive activity in the sector of their absorption. This policy if properly implemented may also succeed in realising the potential capital accumulation which remains concealed in disguised unemployment. The problem of urban unemployment in India has assumed two forms. First, the failure of the industrial sector to grow at a fast enough rate to absorb the growing urban population has resulted in what is usually called industrial unemployment. Secondly, expansion of general education has created unending demand for white collar jobs which the country's urban economy has failed to meet. Thus the ranks of educated unemployed continue to swell and presently a solution to this problem is not in sight.

Scarcity of capital- Of all factors of economic development, capital is considered to be the most important. In fact it is the accumulation of capital that alone can help a country in its attempt to overcome its economic backwardness. Kuznets has very aptly remarked, "Low capital formation proportions means low rates of growth of national product, unless capital-output ratio declines, i.e., unless more output can be turned out per unit of capital. Since there is a continuous shift in favour of capital-intensive techniques in the Third World countries, capital-output ratio cannot be expected to fall. Therefore, if these countries have to grow, they have no choice except to raise their rates of capital accumulation. This has been precisely India's problem during the last five decades. In 1950-60 the gross saving-investment rates in this country was around 8.9 per cent. Obviously at this rate of capital formation, the country could not hope to record any impressive economic growth. Over the planning period both saving and investment rates have risen. In 1970-71 rates of gross domestic saving and gross domestic capital formation were 14.6 and 15.4 per cent respectively. Since then both saving and investment rates have registered modest growth.

According to the estimates of C.S.O., rates of gross domestic saving and gross domestic capital formation in 1990-91 were 23.1 and 26.3 per cent respectively. Subsequently there was a decline both in the rate of gross domestic saving and the rate of gross domestic capital formation. In 2001-02 the rates of gross domestic saving and gross domestic capital formation were estimated to be 23.5 and 22.9 per cent respectively. These rates of saving and capital formation are enough to realise only a modest rate of growth. This

explains why in India the rate of growth remained stuck at a relatively low level. Strangely, estimates of saving and investment for 2003-04 and quick estimates of saving and investment for 2004-05 announced by the CSO surprised everybody. The gross domestic saving rate for 2004-05 has been estimated to be as high as 31.3 per cent by the CSO while gross investment rate in this year has also been claimed to have risen to 31.5 per cent. In 2005-06 the rates of gross domestic saving and gross domestic capital formation continued to rise. They stood at 32.4 per cent and 33.8 per cent respectively. This implies that in 4 years period saving and investment rates have increased by 9-10 percentage points which seems to be doubtful. According to Economic and Political Weekly editorial (February 12, 2005), "The investment rate, which stands at 26.6 per cent for the year (2003-04) according to accepted commodity flow method, when adjusted for 'errors and omissions' is pushed to 28.0 per cent. This is an indefensible procedure. When the figures are examined carefully the domestic saving and investment rates stand at a more modest 25 per cent and 23 per cent respectively.

In contrast, the rates of economic growth have been remarkably high in some of the East- Asian countries. All these countries had the rates of saving and capital formation consistently over 35 per cent of GDP for long periods. High rates of saving and capital formation allow an economy to grow at a fast rate, introduce latest technologies and become internationally competitive.

Technological backwardness- While technological progress is at the heart of development process, over a wide range of productive activity, techniques of production are backward in India. Agriculture which provides subsistence to about two- thirds of the population is even now characterized by highly backward techniques. Except in the green revolution belt of the country everywhere else farmers are persisting with centuries old outmoded production techniques. Their failure to switch over to modern techniques, however, cannot be explained in terms of their ignorance. Modern technology is certainly scale neutral, but it is not resource neutral. Therefore the small and marginal farmers who constitute the overwhelming majority have, on account of their poverty failed to adopt new technology which in turn has kept agricultural productivity appallingly low. However in large- scale industries, energy, transport and communications sectors modern production techniques have been introduced. Nevertheless there still exists wide gap between the sophisticated production techniques of the developed countries and India's technology. Over the years this country has built up substantial capability in science and technology and if it harnesses this resource in a purposeful manner it can overcome one of its major obstacles to economic development.

Lack of entrepreneurs- Joseph A. Schumpeter has assigned a vital role to entrepreneurs in his theory of growth. According to him, "the function of entrepreneurs is to reform or revolutionize the pattern of production by exploiting an invention or, more generally, an untried technological possibility for producing a new commodity or producing an old one in a new way by opening up a new source of supply of raw materials or a new outlet for products, by reorganizing an industry and so on. Obviously these activities require aptitudes that are present only in a small fraction of population. Therefore, if some society possesses people who are gifted with entrepreneurial skills, it is bound to grow rapidly. Some economic historians contend that the presence of this class in England, Germany and the U.S.A had a

major role in their development. In contrast, such a class did not exist during the British period in India. Even in the later phase of the British rule the private enterprise did not fulfill any of the basis conditions of economic growth. During post- Independence period the role of private enterprise in development has been most disappointing. The country even now does not seem to have many Schumpeterian innovating entrepreneurs. Industrialists in India generally concentrate on quick; speculative profits rather than on the long- terms industrial development of the country. From this point of view information technology sector is an exception. In this industry there are some good entrepreneurs like N.R. Narayan Murthy and Azim Premji. However, they have failed to inspire industrialists in other sectors. JRD Tata and Reliance industries founder Dhirubhai Ambani still remain the role models and it is difficult to name any other entrepreneur in the industrial sectors.

Policy Prior to 1991

A large number of steps were initiated by the Government of India after independence for the development of small- scale and cottage industries. These included the building up of organizational structure, increase in the outlay for the development of small-scale and cottage industries, reservations for production, credit and marketing facilities, concessions, exemptions etc.

1. **Organisational Structure-** (I) A Cottage Industries Board was set up in 1947 itself. This was split into the following three boards during the First Five Years Plan- All India Handloom Board, all India Handicraft Boards, and All India Khadi and Village Industries Board. In addition three more boards were set up. These were the small scale industries board, Coir Board and Central Silk Board. Thus at the end of the First Five Year Plan, there were a total of six boards covering the entire field of small- scale and cottage industries. Together, they constituted the organisational structure through which the promotional and developmental efforts of the State were to be carried out.

(II) National Small Industries corporation Ltd. (NSIC) was set- up in 1955 to provide machinery to small- scale units on hire- purchase basis and to assist

(III) Four Regional Small Industries Service Institutes, with a number of branches were set up to provide technical assistance to the small- scale industries.

(IV) Small Industries Development Organisation (SIDO) was set up in 1954. It these unit in procuring order from government departments and offices. Functions as an apex body in the formulation of policies and coordination of institutional activities for sustained and organized growth of small- scale industries. It has a large network of small industries service institutes, branch institutes, tool rooms etc.

(V) The programme of Industrial Estates was initiated in 1955. The programme aims at providing factory accommodation and a number of common facilities like power, water, transport etc. at one place.

(VI) The programme of District Industries Centre (DICs) was introduced In May 1979. The idea was to establish one agency in each district called the District Industries Centre to provides and arrange a package of assistance and facilities for credit guidance, raw materials, training, marketing etc. including the necessary help to unemployed educated young entrepreneur in general and custom services. At present there are 422 DICs operating in the country covering 431 districts (except Mumbai, Kolkata, Delhi and Chennai).

2. **Plan Expenditure-** Expenditure on small- scale and cottage industries has increased considerably over the plans. It was Rs. 42 crore in the First Plan, Rs. 187 crore in the Second Plan, Rs. 1,945 crore in the Sixth Plan (1980-85), Rs. 3,249 crore in the seventh Plan (1985-90) and Rs. 7,266 crore in the Eight Plan (1992-97). Expenditure on small- scale and cottage industries in the Ninth Plan (1997-2002) is estimated at Rs. 8,384 crore.

3. **Reservation for SSIs-** To protect small- scale and units from competition from large-scale units, government has reserve the production of a large number of items for the small-scale sector. The list of reserved items was expanded from 77 to 124 in the Fourth Plan to 500 in 1977 and further to 873 items on October 18, 1984 (on July 31, 1989 the number of reserved items stood at 836).

4. **Financial assistance for SSIs-** Several schemes were introduced to provide financial assistance to small- scale industries. These include - the small industries Development Fund (SIDF) in 1986, National Equity Fund (NEF) in 1987 and the Single Window Schemes (SWS) in 1988. SIDF provides re-finance assistance for development, expansion, diversification and rehabilitation of small-scale, cottage and village industries and tiny sector in rural areas. NEF provides equity type support to small entrepreneurs for setting up new projects in tiny/small scale sector and also assistance for rehabilitation of viable sick units in the small-scale sector. SWS provides working capital loans along with terms loans for fixed capital to new tiny and small-scale units.

In addition, commercial banks were asked to provide priority to small-scale and cottage industries in granting credit facilities. For this purpose, procedures and conditions of financial assistance from commercial banks and other institutions have been liberalised.

5. **Setting up of SIDBI-** For meeting the long standing demand of small-scale industries for a separate Apex Bank to provide financial assistance to them, the government set-up the small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) in 1989. With a view to ensuring larger flow of assistance to the small-scale units, the immediate thrust of SIDBI was on (I) initiating steps for technological upgradation and modernization of existing units; (II) expanding the channels for marketing the products of the small-scale sector; and (III) promotion of employment-oriented industries especially in semi-urban areas to create more employment opportunities. SIDBI provides assistance to the small-scale units through the existing credit delivery system comprising State Financial Corporations, State Industrial Development Corporations, Commercial Banks, Co-operative Banks, and Regional Rural Banks. The major activities of SIDBI are: (I) refinance of loans and advances; (II) discounting and re-discounting of bills; (III) extension of seed capital/soft loans; (IV) granting direct assistance and refinancing of loans; (V) providing services like factoring, leasing etc; and (VI) extending financial support to State Small Industrial Development Corporations.

6. **Other measures-** A number of other measures were introduced from time to time to promote the growth of small-scale and cottage industries. Some of these measures were as follows:

(I) A Council for Advancement of Rural Technology (CART) was set up in October 1982 to provide the necessary technical input to the rural industries.

(II) Price and purchase preference was granted to products manufactured in the small-scale sector in government purchase programme.

(III) Excise concessions were granted to both registered and unregistered units on a graded scale depending on turnover upto Rs. 300 lakh.

(IV) Full exemption was granted upto a turnover of Rs. 30 lakh and concessional rate of excise duty was levied for a turnover exceeding Rs. 30 lakh but not exceeding Rs. 75 lakh.

New Small Enterprise Policy, 1991

The government announced a policy package for small, tiny and village industries in August 1991 with the primary objective of imparting more vitality and growth impetus to this sector. Important measures announced in this policy were as under:

1. The investment limit for tiny units was raised from Rs. 2 lakh to Rs. 5 lakh. Moreover the locational restrictions were done away with. This opened up the way for tiny units within the new investments limit and located in bigger towns (population of more than 50,000) to become a part of 'tiny' group. In addition while earlier on 'industry' meant, by and large, manufacturing, the new policy widened the scope to include industry-related service and business enterprises. This, according to Sandesara, is more realistic. Like in many other countries, now our country has a 'small business policy' and not a 'small industry policy'.

2. The 1991 policy proposed a separate package for the promotion of tiny enterprises. While these enterprises were to receive various types of support on a continuing basis, other (non-tiny) small enterprises were to be mainly entitled to one-time benefits (like preference in land allocation/power connections, access to facilities for skill/technology upgradation). The philosophy underlying this seemed to be to help the tiny units to grow faster upto a certain limit (with assistance), after which they were expected to generate their own momentum of growth, so that less frequent assistance would then suffice.

3. The third major change related to equity participation. The 1991 policy provided for equity participation by other industrial units in the small-scale units not exceeding 24 per cent of the total shareholding. This is expected to prove mutually beneficial both to large units and the small, especially ancillary units, and further cement the economic bonds between the two sectors. This provision not only relieves the small units of the burden of full equity funding, but also builds up the stakes of large units in the survival and growth of small units.

4. The fourth important feature was the introduction of a new legal form of organization of business, namely, restricted or limited partnership. In this form, the liability of at least one partner is unlimited, whereas other partners have their liability limited to invested capital. This is a welcome provision. It will attract equity capital from friends and relatives of the small-scale entrepreneurs who may like to help their kith and kin but who were earlier reluctant due to unlimited liability in the partnership form.

5. Some other features of the policy were:

(I) The policy proposed to meet the entire credit demand of the small and tiny units. The emphasis was shifted from 'cheapness of credit' to 'adequacy of credit'.

(II) The scope of the National Equity Fund (NEF) scheme and Single Window Scheme (SWS) was enlarged.

(III) The policy provided for according priority to the tiny sector in the government purchase programme.

(IV) The small and tiny sector was to be accorded priority in allocation of indigenous raw materials.

(V) The policy envisaged market promotion of small and tiny sectors products to be undertaken by cooperatives, public sector institutions and other professional agencies.

(VI) The policy proposed a scheme of integrated infrastructure development for small industries to facilitate location of industries in rural and backward areas and to promote stronger co-ordination between industry and agriculture. The scheme was formally launched in March 1994 and Integrated Infrastructure Development Centre (IIDCs) set up.

The Ninth Plan emphasized dereservation as it argued that dereservation would help a number of SSI units to upgrade their technology, improve the quality of their products, expand their scale of operations, and boost their exports. However, dereservation is to be done in such a way that it does not cause any "sudden dislocation and problem for the weak small scale units. The plan recognizes that the biggest problem facing the small-scale sector is inadequate availability of credit and purposes a number of initiatives in this regard. These include (I) strengthening the financial and management base of State Financial Corporations and Small Industries Development Organisation to enable them to provide better services to the small scale sector; (II) setting up specialized branches by banks for financing small-scale industries; (III) setting up of Local Areas Banks (LABs) by financially strong and better managed SSI association; (VI) encouraging non- banking financial companies (NBFCs) through suitable financial incentives to provide more loans to the SSI units, etc.

Comprehensive Policy Package 2000 and Recent Policy Measures

A comprehensive policy package for the small-scale sector was announced by the Prime Minister on August 30, 2000. The main elements of this package were: (1) Conducting the third census of small-scale industries; (2) raising the exemption for excise duty limit from Rs. 50 lakh to Rs. 1 crore to improve the competitiveness of small-scale sector; (3) providing credit linked capital subsidy of 12 per cent against loans for technology upgradation in specified industries; (4) raising the limit of investment in industry related service and business enterprises from Rs. 5 lakh to Rs. 10 lakh ; (5) raising the limit of composite loans from Rs. 10 lakh to Rs. 25 lakh; (6) encouraging SSI association to develop and operate testing laboratories; (7) constitution of group under the cabinet Secretary to suggest/recommend streamlining of inspection and repeal of redundant laws and regulations applicable to the sector: (8) increasing the coverage of Integrated Infrastructure Development (IID) scheme to progressively covers all areas in the country with 50 per cent reservation for rural areas and 50 per cent of plots-earmarked for tiny sector, etc.

As stated earlier, the Third Census of the small-scale sector covering both registered and unregistered (units) was conducted during the year 2001-02. This has provided valuable information regarding the SSI sector. Other important steps undertaken in recent years are as follows:

1. **Raising of Investment Limit-** While the investment limit for the SSI sector is presently Rs. 1.5 crore, a specific list of hi-tech and export-oriented units has been brought out for which the investment limit has been raised to Rs. 5 crore to facilitate there suitable technology upgradation so that they can maintain their competitive edge.

2. **Enhancing the excise exemption limit-** As announced in the Budget 2005-06, the turnover eligibility limit under the general SSI Excise Exemption Scheme has been raised from Rs. 3 crore to Rs. 4 crore.
3. **Scheme to address the problem of collaterals-** To address the problem of collaterals faced by the SSI units, a credit Guarantee fund (schemes) has been launched to provide guarantee for loans upto Rs. 25 lakh extended by commercial banks, selected well performing Regional Rural Banks and other Financial Institutions without any collateral including third party guarantee. A Credit Guarantee Trust Fund has been created to implement the scheme.
4. **Scheme for technology upgradation-** To encourage technology upgradation, a credit linked capital subsidy scheme for technology upgradation has been launched. Under this scheme, 15 per cent capital subsidy is admissible on loans upto Rs. 1 crore, advance by scheduled commercial banks/State Finance Corporations/ National Small Industries Corporations to small-scale industries for technology upgradation.
5. **Extension of IID-** The Integrated Infrastructure Development (IID) scheme has been extended to cover the entire country with 50 per cent reservation for rural areas.
6. **Market Development Assistance-** A new scheme named Market Development Assistance (MDA) was launched exclusively for the SSI sector.
7. **Dereservation-** In recent years, the government has been following the policy of dereservation as it believes that this will help the SSIs units to upgrade their technology and improve the quality of their products. As a result of this policy, the number of items reserved for the SSI sector came down from 836 in July 1989 to 239 on January 22, 2007 and further to only 114 in March 2007.
8. **Credit delivery to SSI Sector-** To ensure credit delivery to the SSI sector, a number of steps have been undertaken in recent years: (I) the composite loan limit has been raised from Rs. 50 lakh to Rs. 1 crore; (II) the limit of collateral free loans has been raised from Rs.15 lakh to Rs. 25 lakh in case of SSI units with a good track record; (III) Laghu Udyami Credit Card (LUCC) scheme has been liberalised by enhancing the credit limit for Rs. 2 lakh to Rs. 10 lakh, for borrowers having a satisfactory track record; (IV) the Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) Fund of Rs. 10,000 crore was operationalised by the SIDBI (Small Industries Development Bank of India) since April 2004. Eighty per cent of the lending from this Fund will be for SSI units, at interest rate of 2 per cent below the prevailing PLR (prime lending rate) of the SIDBI.

As a result of all these efforts, there has been a considerable expansion of bank credit to the small-scale sector in recent years. As at the end of March 2006, the amount of bank credit outstanding against small-scale industries stood at Rs.82,434 crore which was 8.1 per cent of gross bank credit and 20.1 per cent (i.e., one-fifth) of total priority sector advances by banks.

9. **Enactment of SMED Act, 2006-** Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Development (SMED) Act was enacted in 2006. It provides the first-ever legal framework for recognition of the concept of "enterprises" (comprising both manufacturing and services) and integrating the three tiers of these enterprises, viz., micro, small and medium. It also provides for a statutory consultative mechanism at the national level with wide representation of all sections of stakeholders, particularly the three classes of enterprises. Other important provisions of the

Act are (I) establishment of specific fund for the promotion, development and enhancement of competitiveness of these enterprises; (II) notification of schemes/programmes for the purpose; (III) progressive credit policies and practices; (IV) preference in government procurements to products and services of the micro and small enterprises; (V) more effective mechanisms for mitigating the problems of delayed payments to micro and small enterprises; and (VI) simplification of the process of closure of business by all three categories of enterprises.

Critical Evaluation of the Policy for Small-Scale Industries

Massive growth has taken place in the small-scale sector during the period of planning. This sector now contributes over 39 per cent to the gross turnover in the manufacturing sector, 45 per cent of manufacturing exports and 33 per cent (i.e., one-third) of total exports. The government claims that a substantial part of the growth was due to its promotional efforts. However, a number of scholars have challenged this view. Their main points of criticism are as follows:

1. While there has been a substantial growth in modern small-scale industries falling within the preview of SIDO (Small Industries Development Organisation), this development has remained concentrated in main cities and large towns. Moreover, only a few units account for a substantial part of the output of this sector.

2. Institutional credit has generally gone to a small percentage of small-scale units.

3. There is considerable under-utilisation of capacity and sickness in the small-scale sector.

4. According to Rakesh Mohan, inspite of the vast increase in the number of reserved items, much of the growth in the small-scale sector seems to be in products lines outside the reserved list. It is quite possible that the policy of reservation might actually be protecting inefficient units in stagnant Industries.

5. Rakesh Mohan has argued that SSI product reservations had a very adverse effects on the growth of exports. To substantiate his assertion, he divides the export commodity groups into five broad categories on the basis of skill and technology. Group I consists of primary commodities including processed foods; Group II consists of labour intensive and resource based industries requiring low levels of technology (textiles, clothing and footwear, toys and sports equipment, wood and paper products etc.); Group III consists of sector that require low to medium levels of technology sophistication (iron and steel, transport equipment etc.); Group IV consists of industries with medium to high levels of technology sophistication (rubber and plastic products, non-electrical machinery and motor vehicles); and Group V consists of industries requiring highest level of technology sophistication (chemical and pharmaceutical products, computer and office equipment ,scientific instrument etc). All key industrializing nations of Asia that started industrialization along with India shifted rapidly from Group I to Group II and then to higher levels of technological sophistication so much so that they now export larger quantities of goods falling in Groups IV and V. This has helped them in increasing exports earnings substantially. They key success stories here are Indonesia, Malaysia and Thailand. In all these countries, the 'initial kick' in export growth was provided by Group II industries. However, the Indian

exports exhibit a relatively unchanging structure since the early 1980s and the country seems to be stuck up with Group II products. Thus the export product composition exhibits a stagnant picture. Rakesh Mohan opines that since a very high proportion of items in Group II are reserved for small scale industries in India, India's policies on small scale reservation have had an adverse effect on Indian export performance.

6. Another significant observation made by Rakesh Mohan is that contrary to the belief that SSIs help in industrial dispersal and promote the development of backward areas, there has been spatial concentration of these industries in 'clusters' in particular product lines. For instance, more than 81 per cent of SSEs (small scale enterprises) are concentrated in 204 districts, and more than 50 per cent of the districts do not have any significant number of small enterprises.

7. Though employment in the small scale sector has been rising, it is totally inadequate to solve the problem of unemployment in the rural areas. Even in urban areas, the employment opportunities in the small-scale sector have arisen mainly in large metropolitan cities. Moreover, a comparison with other large Asian countries show that Indian manufacturing employment growth has been the lowest over the past three or four decades. In a study released in 1992, Bhavani found that policies intended to favour small industries (reservation, financial incentives, etc.) are neither promoting employment nor improving the competitive base of small firms. Rather, they are working as strong disincentives of growth of small firms. The support measures gives protected enterprises an incentives not to grow out of small scale sector moreover, giving the fact that substantial incentives have all along been giving to the large firms and public sector undertaking as well (as would be clear from the fact that India's byzantine structure of import and export regulation, licensing procedures, quantitative restrictions, high traffic walls, etc., have all favoured these firms), Ira N. Gang argues that "it is difficult to see what the general thrust of government policies has been to encourage the small or the large firms -even with in any given industry.

PROBLEMS FACED BY SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES (SSI) IN INDIA:

SSIs face a number of problems. Here is a brief mention of some such problems:

1. Poor Financial Management

Scarcity of finance and credit is perhaps the greatest challenge in the proper functioning of SSIs in India. Capital base of small scale units is very weak. It is an irony that at times these small scale units even fail to manage their working capital properly. Poor financial management of small scale units is a cause of worry as it results in high mortality of small scale units.

2. Problem of Infrastructure, Availability of raw material, Machines and Equipments etc.

This is ridiculous that small scale sector of India has to face severe problems due to inadequacy of basic inputs such as infrastructural facilities, availability of raw material, machine and equipment etc. In a survey of 1,063 firms, Keshav Das and Sebastian Morris found that 716 firms (or more than 67 percent) said that they faced significant infrastructural problems. This fact speaks of the severity of the problem. "Machinery and other equipment in many small industries has grown obsolescent. On account of this reason

while their costs of production are high, the quality is inferior as compared to the large scale units. Moreover, the small scale units often do not care about the changing tastes and fashions of the people. Accordingly, modernisation and rationalisation are urgently required in small scale industries. •

3. Problem of marketing and poor data base:

Large scale industries have an advantage over small scale industries as far as marketing of products is concerned. Small scale Industries mainly flourish in backward areas where roads are in a very pitty state. In one of the economic surveys of India it was rightly pointed out that "Indian roads are greatest hinderance in foreign direct investment to India. Due to poor infrastructural facilities coupled with shortage of capital and financial resources, small scale units do not have adequate 'staying capacity' and are often forced to sell their products at unremunerative prices.

Proper data base is a pre-requisite for framing economic policies in modern times. Unfortunately, both leading organizations engaged in collecting information about small scale sector, i.e. Small Industries Development Organization (SIDO) and Central Statistical Organization (CSO) fail to provide complete information on small scale sector.

"There is an urgent need for evolving regular system for the up-gradation and collection of data on the SSI sector in view of the rapid growth and substantial contribution of the SSI sector. New units come up every year for different lines of production, while existing units either diversify or expand or in certain cases close down. Upkeep of latest information is critical for policy decisions.

POLICY MEASURE TAKEN TO REVAMP SMALL SCALE SECTORS (SSS):

After having discussed the role of SSI sector in Indian economy and the problems faced by this sector in India, present section of the research offers certain corrective measures or suggestions to revamp Indian SSI sector. Revamping of SSI sector is of vital concern for overall socio-economic health of our nation.

1. Changes in the structure and pattern of Management Education being offered in India

Indian education system has witnessed a spate of professional education institutes during last around one and a half decade. It will not be unfair to say that Management Education has been a front runner in the boom of professional education institutes in India. The curriculum designed for these Management Courses is predominantly influenced by western pattern. There are almost negligible courses on SSI's and Entrepreneurial development in curriculum of MBA. Our Management Education mainly puts emphasis on management of large scale business. The curriculum borrowed from developed nations of west perhaps fails to adequately recognize the importance and significance of SSI in Indian circumstances.

There is an urgent need to mould the management education in tune with our needs and circumstances particularly with reference to SSIs. Government's initiative and funds are failing to revamp SSI sector. Indian Higher Education System has rapidly created creditable infrastructure through private initiative in the area of Management Education. Only a slight orientation and careful planning will take care of the rest.

2. Need to expand the ambit of Corporate Governance to cover SSI

Separation of ownership and control lies in the heart of talks and debates concerning Corporate Governance. Due to its vary nature Corporate Governance is more akin to the companies having share holding features. SSUs generally don't have shareholders as their scale of operations is not large enough to get the company listed on share market. "Studies of firms in India and abroad have shown that markets and investors take notice of well-managed companies, respond positively to them, and reward such companies, with higher valuations. A common feature of such companies is that they have systems in place which allow sufficient freedom to the boards and management to take decisions towards the progress of their companies and to innovate, while remaining within a framework of effective accountability. In other wards they have a system of good Corporate Governance"¹⁰. Corporate Governance will inject a sense of discipline and system in SSI sector of India which will go a long way in shapping fortunes of this vital sector of Indian economy.

Setting up of National Knowledge Commission (NKC) of India under the chairmanship of Sam Pitroda is a welcome sign. Prime Minister Manmohan Singh was instrumental behind this development. NKC aims at protecting India's traditional knowledge which forms the backbone of many village and cottage industries. "Traditional or indigenous knowledge is the systematic body of knowledge acquired by local people through the accumulation of experience, informal experiment and intimate understanding of local conditions and provides a productive context for activities designed to help the communities. Traditional knowledge is the product of centuries of trial and error, natural selection and keen observation that can form a knowledge base on which researchers and extension worker can plan their research strategy and experimental procedures". It is interesting to point out here that knowledge commission takes into consideration traditional knowledge which has a direct relationship with India's age old traditional small scale industries but this aspect of traditional knowledge gets heavily diluted when it comes to Corporate Governance. National Knowledge Commission and Corporate Governance committee need to work in tandem with each other to facilitate proper growth of SSI sector of India. "Corporate Governance is not restricted to the organization or profession. Its ambit envelops the society by holding a balance between economic and social goals and between individual and communal goals. The governance framework is there to encourage the efficient use of resources and equality to require accountability for the stewardship of human resources. The aim is to align as nearly as possible the individuals, corporation and society. The incentive for states is to strengthen their economies and discourage fraud and mismanagement.

CONCLUSION:

Small scale industries thus have a great socio-economic worth for India. There is an urgent need to revamp the system of small scale industries. Policies must be revisited and appropriate initiatives must be taken to revamp this sector. Collective bargaining is the hallmark of democratic sentiments. Democratisation of politics, economy or society, all follow this basic principle of collective bargaining. Strengthening at grass root level enhances the potential of collective bargaining of an economy. This potential of collective bargaining at grass root level is of vital concern for infusing a democratic sense and feeling in the economy.

Small scale industries are sometimes referred to as micro enterprises or 'the world's smallest business.' "According to Economic census of 1990, only about 5% of the world's entrepreneurs have access to financial services. Currently, the microfinance sector globally is reaching approximately 4% of that potential market."10 In the process of democratization of Indian economy, the most fundamental units are these micro and small enterprises. However, non-availability of finance weakens the true potential of these small units of economy as the basic entities of economic democracy.

It is quite ironical that mortality rate of small scale firm is very high in India and around 95% of them die within first five years of their existence. Non-availability of working capital becomes cause of their premature death. Small scale units are playing vital role in India's overall socio-economic fabric and all efforts must be taken to present their vital socio-economic character. In a developing country like India, the role and importance of small-scale industries is very significant towards poverty eradication, employment generation, rural development and creating regional balance in promotion and growth of various development activities It is estimated that this sector has been contributing about 40% of the gross value of output produced in the manufacturing sector and the generation of employment by the small-scale sector is more than five times to that of the large-scale sector. This clearly shows the importance of small-scale industries in the economic development of the country. The small-scale industry have been playing an important role in the growth process of Indian economy since independence in spite of stiff competition from the large sector and not very encouraging support from the government.

References

Reference Books:

- Alien, Louis L, Starting and Succeeding in Your OWN Small Business, Grossat & Dunlop, New York, 1968
- Anyor, Jay G., Entrepreneurial Dimensions of Management, Livingstone Pub. Co., W Piers, 1973.
- Anderson, D., Small Industries in Developing Countries-Some issues, Working Paper 518, World Bank, Washington D.C.
- Antony Valsomma, "Education and Employment: The key to women Empoverment", Kuruskhetra, 2005. Apparao P.B., Personnel Problems in small scale Industries, Deep & Deep, New Delhi, 1988
- Bala, S, Management of Small Scale Industry, Deep & Deep, New Delhi 1983
- Bala Krishnan G., Financing of Small Scale Industries, Himalaya, Bombay, 1990
- Baumbach, C.M., Basic Small Business Management, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, 1983.
- Buffa, E.S., Production Management, Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1992
- Chandra, P., Projects - Preparation, Appraisal and Implementation, Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi, 1995.
- Davidson, J; and A. sanow, You can Start Your Own Small Business, Washington Pub, 1991
- Desai, Vasant, Problems and Prospects of Small Scale Industries, Himalaya, Bombay, 1989
- Deshpande, M.V., Entrepreneurship of Small Scale Industries, Deep & Deep, New Delhi, 1982.
- Development Commissioner SSI, Industrial Design Aid to Small Industries, New Delhi
- Government of India, Guidelines for preparation of Feasibility Reports for Industrial Projects, Planning Commission, New Delhi, 1981
- Khanka S.S., Industrial Sickness in India, Commonwealth, New Delhi, 1994

C. M. Jain & Neeraj Manchanda / A critical study on Small Scale Sector before and after Liberalization

- Kapur Premita(ed.)- “Empowering the Indian women”, Publications Division, Ministry of Information are Broad casting, Government of India, Patiala House, New Delhi, 2001.
- Misra Satyabraka and Pattnaik Satyanarayane. “.ender Dimensions of HIV/AzDs, Kurukshetra, A Journal on Rural Development, New Delhi, vol. 54, No. 4 Feb. 2006.
- Narashiman, S. “Empovering women”, Yojna vol. 44 (9) Sep. 2000.
- Pathak, H.N., Small Scale Industries in the Next Decade, IIM Ahmedabad, 1978
- Pattnain B.K. “women Entrepreneurship”, Poorvi Pras Ltd. Rajkot, 1999.
- Samchita Trikpathi, “Women Leadership and Pachayati Raj Institution”, Kurshetra, Nov. 2005.
- Thomas E.C. “Protection of the Rights of women”, Employment News, weekly, New Delhi, vol. xx, No. 33, 12-18 Nov. 2005.
- Vepa, Ram., Modern Small Industries in India, Sage Publications, New Delhi, 1988

Annual Reports, Journals, Magazines & News Papers

- Annual Reports of Ministry of Human Resource (Govt of India) (2003-04 to 2007-08)
 - Annual Reports of Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Govt of India) (2003-04 to 2004-08)
 - Ashish Bose, “Employment of Women: How and When, Economic and Political Weekly, August 19-25, 2000.
 - T.R. Gurusurthy: Self Employment-Group Empower Rural Women, Kurukshetra, February, 2000.
 - Dr. Najma Heptulla, “Role of Women in Population Stabilisation, Yojna August, 2000.
 - Dr. Sanjdeep “Corporate Women: A Symbol of Women Empowerment” in “Women Empowerment- Today’s Vision Fro Tommorow’s Vision”,
 - Ed. Meenu Agarwal, Maharaja Publicataion, Delhi, 2007.
-
- Business Standard
 - Economic Surveys
 - Economic Times
 - Financial Express
 - National Financial Budgets
 - The Hindu
 - Times of India